

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING PRIMARY CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Educating young people to become free-thinking, innovative and well-rounded people is carried out from primary grades, this process is one of the important tasks. For this reason, the content of education is being fundamentally updated. This article provides the necessary information about the use of interactive methods in teaching primary classes.

In the period of junior school age, motivations for independent education arise in the child, and they arise in the simplest form - with interest in additional resources and reading books on various topics along with acquiring knowledge. Education is a cooperative activity of the teacher and students, and in this process, the development of the individual, his education and upbringing is realized. In the lessons, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to students through exercises, and students acquire the ability to use them as a result of mastering them. In the process of learning, students use different forms of learning, that is, they rely on specific differences in receiving, processing and applying the information being learned. In the course of education, issues of education and upbringing are solved in the form of cooperation between teachers and students during classes, independent work of students, extracurricular activities. The purpose of

education is formed according to the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate. The goal of education in scientific literature is to create skills and competencies, develop logical-creative thinking, improve communicative literacy, inculcate the national idea, form oriental education, define personality it is emphasized that it consists of spiritual enrichment. Based on the educational goal, students' communication culture is improved by increasing their independent thinking, oral and written literacy, and developing logical thinking. On the basis of the educational goal, spiritual, ideological and sophisticated education is provided. In the process of language learning, there is an opportunity to get closer to the cultural and moral values of the people. One of the great sages said, "If you live with anxiety about the future, give your children a good education and teach them." It would not be wrong to say that the reforms implemented

in the education system in our country are not a work aimed at achieving results in one or two years or in a short period of time, but in the real sense, it is a change that will last for several hundred years. This shows that our president cares about our future, our future generation, and the idea that all the children of our country - my children, they should be stronger, more educated and definitely happier than us - is a wise policy. In education, attention is focused on the issue of teaching the student to think, to understand the opinion of others and to be able to express this opinion in oral and written form. takes place. The way of life and cultural creativity of the nation is studied on the basis of its rich historical heritage. Today, the teacher is required to use advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in the educational process. Based on the above, based on our experiences, we present our thoughts on the ways of teaching and training by using interactive methods in classes. We think that it will provide practical help to our colleagues in improving the effectiveness of training sessions. Also, he becomes one of the close assistants of students in fulfilling the responsible task of choosing their direction and forming the skills of preparation for independent life. Below we give recommendations on the implementation of modern methods of teaching based on certain topics in the classroom. You use it in a creative way and try to find an answer to the question of our first president: "What are we doing today to instill in our children feelings of pride, pride, and devotion to our motherland, which is sacred for every age" - We hope that you will contribute to achieving the intended goal by implementing modern methods of

education. When teaching students in primary grades, especially in the first grade, it is necessary to take into account the age, physiological and psychological characteristics of the student. The use of game technologies in education is one of the most effective tools. During the game, their thinking, outlook, and thinking will expand. Scientists believe that the game approach to education facilitates the learning process. It not only makes it easier, but also increases the interest in this subject and encourages the child to acquire deep knowledge. Game-style lessons help children develop their oral language. First graders really like different visuals with pictures or videos. Games should be regularly used to develop their speech through different colored pictures. For example, What is this?, Who is this?, Who knows the most words? games like During the game, it is necessary to encourage children to remember words and pronounce them correctly. Some of the best teaching methods that can be implemented in elementary schools are:

1. Visualization Bring boring scientific concepts to life through visual and hands-on learning experiences, helping students understand how they apply to real life.
2. Cooperative Learning Encourage students to work cooperatively by encouraging small group or whole class activities.
3. Inquiry-Based Instruction Encouraging students to ask questions and explore their own ideas helps them improve their problem-solving skills and deepen their understanding of scientific concepts. Both are important life skills.
4. Differentiation Differentiate and define the learning process by dividing tasks

according to students' abilities so that no one is left behind.

5. Professional Development Participating in regular professional development

programs is a great way to improve a teacher's teaching skills.

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